

An Aerodynamic Design and Analysis of Motor Cycle Helmet with Anti-Glare Visor

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Abstract : Motor cycle accidents have been increased in the last two decades. Helmet can protect the vehicle riders from severe injuries during road accident to certain extent. To design a functional helmet, it is important to analyze the shape of the helmet and visor portion. So that the attempt has been made for design and analysis of new helmet by considering the drag pressure and anti-glare visor. The drag pressure resistance presses the helmet against the neck portion of the rider. The shape of an aerodynamic helmet can be able to reduce the drag pressure. The spherical shape and a new aerodynamic shape helmets are designed with aid of Pro-E software and the drag pressure are calculated and comparison has been made on the basis of drag pressure.

Keywords : Helmet, drag pressure, aero-dynamic, refractive index

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